

podaac

Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center

Global Data Assembly Center (GDAC) Report to the GHRSSST Science Team

Edward M. Armstrong¹, Wen-Hao Li¹, Chris Finch

¹Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology

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Session: Agency Reporting

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2019-2020 Highlights

- Several new (12 total) and improved datasets ingested in last 12 months
 - VIIRS, GOES-17, Himawari
 - MISST Arctic campaign Saildrone datasets
- Maintain 50 operational datasets from 12 RDACs, and linkages to NASA CMR and LTSRF archive
- Continued user uptake
 - Several GHRSSST datasets in PO.DAAC top 10
- User community engagement
 - Data in action ocean stories
- Supporting Regional Global Task Sharing (R/G TS) architecture formal proposal and ongoing work
- Improvements to Tools and Services, and Discovery
- Certification as data center with CoreTrustSeal by World Data System
- Working on a new dataset publication framework
- Co-leadership of CEOS SST-VC

Tools, Services and Discovery

- PO.DAAC Earthdata Drive fully implemented.
- State Of The Ocean (SOTO) version 4.5 to be released
 - Includes MODIS v2019.0 L3 (more usable pixels)
 - MUR25 SST and anomalies
 - Progress on SOTO v5 (with data analytics) continues
- HiTIDE
 - GUI based L2 subsetting
- Evaluating the ERDDAP data server
- New mission/measurement themed PO.DAAC web site
 - Will soon use NASA Earthdata Search API for dataset and eventually granule discovery
 - All GHRSSST metadata in the NASA Common Metadata Repository (CMR)
- See posters and presentations by Wen-Hao Li and Ed Armstrong et al. (Session 4) for the full spectrum of PO.DAAC tools and services